

AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM ON MENTAL ALERTNESS AND SELF-CONCEPT OF UNDERPRIVILEGED

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Abstract:

The present study aimed at assessing the level of mental alertness and self-concept among underprivileged. The sample consisted of 100 underprivileged students selected purposively from secondary schools of Kalaburgi and Yadgir districts of Hyderabad Karnataka. A set of questionnaires of mental alertness and self-concept was used. The data analyzed using paired t-test and Pearson's product moment coefficient of correlation. The result revealed that there was a significant difference in mental alertness and self-concept i.e. before and after treatment between gender and domicile. It was also found that the mental alertness and self-concept positively and significantly correlated with each other. The interpretation and summary pertaining to the study were discussed.

Key Words: Intervention Program, Mental Alertness, Self-Concept & Underprivileged

Introduction:

The term adolescence derives from the Latin word *adolescere*, meaning to grow into maturity. It is the transitional period in a person's life between childhood and adulthood. (Rogers, 1981) "A process rather than a time period, a process of achieving the attitudes, and beliefs a needed for effective participation in society".

Relevance of the Study:

An adolescent is the most crucial period of one's life, it is the period of day dreams of adventures, of intense affections and stirring of the heart. The adolescent's emotions are most excitable at this period and at every small suggestion, we find him prepared to do even the impossible. He is subjective and does not know the objective limitations of his power. His mind is pure and holy, he loves everyone and he does not suspect wickedness in other. He has not as yet learned to direct his energies at right and therefore, there is a danger of his going on the wrong path, running on his life. An academically underprivileged student gets disturbed from the social and environmental obstacles. The social and environmental obstacle may impact by negatively among the students learning; they will have found difficulty in remembering, recognizing, writing etc. hence the present study has been carried on the basis of an intervention program on mental alertness and self-concept among underprivileged. In connection with this in the study have chosen the underprivileged and their academic achievement based on that the intervention modules were prepared and same has been followed.

Mental Alertness:

Mental alertness/ability represents an adolescent's brain power in different aspects of competency, including verbal, arithmetical, spatial, and logical reasoning, which is one of the most important functional abilities for a student. The concept of mental health is intrinsically complex. No single and simple formulae can be offered for reducing its rich variety to a dry definition. Though mental health has been a subject of great attention to human kind, yet scholars do not agree on a single definition of it. The general mental alertness plays an important role in adolescent's life especially during the age of 12 to 16 for enhancing their mental ability/alertness. The mental alertness influence on the adolescent's personality in learning towards their academic improvements. The general mental alertness helps in solving the mathematical and verbal etc and environmental barriers of their classroom.

Self-Concept:

Self-concept and self-esteem, attached with identity are often used interchangeably. In fact these are quite distinct. Self-concept is a cognitive structure than the self-esteem, which is an affective reaction, a judgment about one's own self. Self-esteem has become a common word is used in our daily conversation. It is attitude about the self and is related to personal belief about skills, abilities, social relationships and future outcomes. Woolfolk (2004) defines "self-esteem is the value which we place on our own characteristics, abilities and behaviours. Researcher tried to mention two important questions in their research studies. One deals with effect of self-esteem on students' behaviour in school and other deals with consequences of school life on students' self-esteem. Booth and Gerard (2011) reported number of studies in England and United states that explain gender difference in adolescents. Mostly boys have higher self-esteem as compared to girls. Girls are influenced by relationships and boys are influenced by objective success. Whereas Bagley et al (1997) reported in their study that the Canadian schools, girls had significantly lower self-esteem than boys.

Therefore, the present study is aimed at assessing the level of mental alertness and self-concept among underprivileged through an intervention program. Objectives of the present study are to study the level of mental alertness and self-concept among underprivileged before and after intervention program. This study is also find out the relationship between mental alertness and self-concept of underprivileged.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There will be significant difference in mental alertness among underprivileged before and after intervention
- ✓ There will be significant difference in self-concept among underprivileged before and after intervention
- ✓ There will be positive and significant correlation between mental alertness and self-concept among underprivileged.

Methodology:

Operational Definition:

Remedial Training: Specialized instruction for students deviating the expected norm /identifying academic under achievers/slow learner/poor performer and giving them the necessary guidance to help them overcome their problems.

Underprivileged: a student who has below average level of academic achievement and displays no motivation and performs his/her potential.

This study is exploratory in nature and adopts intervention program

Study Area:

The study area included rural and urban taluka of Kalaburagi and Yadgir district. The Kalaburgi and Yadgir cities are class second of Karanataka state, India, which is located 600 kilometer from Bangalore, the capital city of Karnataka.

Data Collection:

The students of Hyderabad Karnataka districts of Yadagir and kalaburgi from government and private aided secondary school students, those who have below average level of potentials

Sample and Techniques:

The present study sample consisted of 100 underprivileged students of couple of districts of Hyderabad Karnataka, out of which 50 are boys and 50 are girls of students. The samples were selected using purposive sampling method. The sample characteristics and the selection of samples are mentioned below.

Academically Underprivileged:

The students of poor academic achievement is considered as academically underprivileged, and the students have shown below his/her level of achievement.

Statistical Techniques:

- ✓ Paired t-test
- ✓ Pearson’s product moment coefficient of correlation

Table 1: Summary of paired sample t-test of mental alertness of academically underprivileged students

Sub-dimension Variables	Pre-test (100)		Post-test (100)		t-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Arithmetic Reasoning	14.80	6.011	17.40	6.059	3.11*
Definition	17.56	7.178	20.89	9.951	2.974*
Number Series	17.78	7.992	17.89	7.764	.099 NS
Same Opposite	16.67	7.522	19.27	6.922	2.389*
Overall	66.81	14.344	75.45	17.587	4.007**

NS: Not significant,

Significant at 0.05, and 0.01**

Above table indicates mean and standard deviation of mental alertness among underprivileged students. Further, paired t-test was employed to examine the effect of remedial training on mental alertness among academically underprivileged students. It was observed that there was a significant impact of remedial training (t=4.007, p<.01). Thus, the sub-dimension wise analysis indicates that the arithmetic reasoning, definition, same opposite was found to be significant at 0.05 level. Whereas, number series sub-dimension was found to be non significant. The reasons behind this student have poor academic achievements, due to lack parental care, environmental effect, and lack of support from the family members. The present study findings agree with Swamy and Kenchappanavar (2016), proper remedial intervention may help students with least performance to overcome their difficulties.

Table 2: Summary of paired t-test on self-concept of academically underprivileged students

Sub-dimension Variables	Pre-test (100)		Post-test (100)		t-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Physical	19.48	5.205	23.07	5.382	4.920***
Social	24.54	5.269	25.61	5.146	1.483

Temperamental	14.84	3.673	20.74	6.190	8.712***
Educational	12.72	3.163	20.48	8.589	8.724***
Moral	23.19	5.875	26.01	5.730	3.440**
Intellectual	13.65	3.724	20.89	9.685	6.852***
Global self-worth	11.25	2.865	18.26	9.422	7.103***
Overall SC	120.74	12.465	153.99	32.043	9.330***

NS: Not significant,

Significant at 0.05, 0.01** and 0.001*** level

A perusal of table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation scores of self-concept of academically underprivileged students. It was observed that there was a significant impact of remedial training on the self-concept of academically, the t-value is 6.852 $p < 0.001$ level. Further sub-dimension wise analysis revealed that physical, temperamental, emotional, moral, intellectual and global self-worth found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.001 level. Whereas, social sub-dimension was found to be non-significant. Thus, it was revealed that Hanan Ebrahim Abd El Aziz Rady, Shabana Kabeer, Mona T. El-Nady (2016) self-concept can affect their academic performance and therefore, be providing proper remedial training students can improve their achievements. Skaalvik, Valas, and Sletta (1994) opined that students with high academic self-concept may focus on out-performing their colleagues academically.

Conclusion:

It was observed that, initially students have performed poorly in basic arithmetic and mental ability and also showed the poor response in self-concept, and after adopting remedial training intervention, it was found that, students' performance was certainly improved. The present study findings suggest that adopting proper remedial intervention for academically poor students can improve their academic performance.

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